

Role of Forensic Accountant in Combating Fraud and other Financial Malfeasance**SAGIR Lawal**

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sagirlawalimam9557@gmail.com; +234 706 097 9557**Abstract**

This study explores the role of forensic accountants in combating fraud and other financial crimes. Employing a survey research design data was collected through primary source via the use of questionnaires. The population of the study consist of 79 members of staff from 3 selected commercial banks in Kano metropolis. Census selection approach was used to arrive at a sample which is a technique in which all the population was used as a sample. Data was analysed via the use of tables and percentages and the hypotheses was tested using chi- Square. The study found that forensic accounting contributes significantly for early detection and prevention of fraud and other financial crimes. It is thus recommended that organisations should invest in comprehensive anti-fraud training programs for employees at all levels.

Keywords: Auditing, Data analysis, Forensic accountants, Fraud, Financial crimes,

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Introduction

Financial crime and fraud have evolved into complex and pervasive challenges that threaten the stability of financial systems, damage corporate reputations, and erode public trust (Levi, 2018). As financial transactions become more intricate and technologies advance, perpetrators of financial crime have also become more sophisticated in their methods (Higgins & Ramesh, 2020). This backdrop necessitates the presence of specialised professionals who possess the knowledge, skills, and acumen to effectively combat these illicit activities. Among these professionals, forensic accountants stand as pivotal figures in the ongoing battle against financial crime and fraud (Oyedokun, Akinwumi, & Asaolu, 2018; Zimbelman & Smith, 2019).

The landscape of financial crime is expansive, encompassing activities such as embezzlement, money laundering, insider trading, tax evasion, and cybercrime. These activities can occur within organisations, across industries, and even on a global scale (Pope & Singleton, 2018). The impacts of financial crime are profound, leading to significant financial losses, tarnished reputations, disrupted business operations, and potential legal ramifications (Sullivan, 2021). As financial criminals devise increasingly sophisticated methods, traditional forms of oversight and regulation often struggle to keep pace (Akinadewo, Asaolu, & Oyedokun, 2020; Bhasin, 2020).

Forensic accounting emerged as a specialised field within the broader realm of accounting to address the evolving nature of financial crime and fraud (Saxena, 2019). Unlike traditional

accounting, which focuses on routine financial reporting and compliance, forensic accounting delves into the examination of financial records, transactions, and activities to uncover irregularities, anomalies, and discrepancies (Oyedokun, Akinwumi, & Asaolu, 2018; Crumbley, 2020). Forensic accountants possess a unique blend of accounting expertise, investigative skills, and legal knowledge, allowing them to navigate the complexities of financial crime investigations (Oyedokun & Asaolu, 2022; Kranacher, Lennox, & Wells, 2011). Forensic accountants play a multifaceted role in combating financial crime and fraud. As detectors and investigators, they are trained to scrutinise financial records, transactions, and documentation for signs of fraud (Wells, 2014). They employ advanced analytical techniques to identify patterns and anomalies that may indicate fraudulent activities. Additionally, they uncover hidden irregularities; financial criminals often engage in intricate schemes to conceal their actions. Forensic accountants possess the ability to trace transactions across multiple accounts and entities, following the money trail to uncover concealed actions (Albrecht et al., 2019).

Collaboration is also key in their role; forensic accountants work closely with law enforcement agencies, legal professionals, and regulatory bodies. Their expertise aids in building strong cases against financial criminals and presenting evidence in legal proceedings (Basioudis & Vasileiou, 2018). Furthermore, forensic accountants contribute to risk assessment and prevention strategies. Beyond investigations, they identify vulnerabilities in financial systems and recommend measures to strengthen internal controls, helping to prevent future instances of financial crime (Wells, 2014).

As financial crime and fraud continue to evolve, the expertise of forensic accountants becomes increasingly indispensable. Their ability to detect, investigate, and address complex financial irregularities plays a crucial role in maintaining the integrity of financial systems, protecting organisations and individuals from harm, and upholding the principles of transparency and accountability (Bhasin, 2020). In light of these challenges and the unique expertise that forensic accountants bring to the table, this proposal seeks to delve into the methodologies, tools, and collaborative strategies that underpin their essential role in combating financial crime and fraud. By examining their contributions and practices, this research aims to shed light on the ways forensic accountants contribute to a more secure and resilient financial landscape.

In contemporary financial environments, the escalation of financial crime and fraud has cast a shadow of uncertainty over economic stability, corporate integrity, and public trust. As financial criminals devise increasingly sophisticated methods to perpetrate illicit activities, traditional methods of oversight and regulation often fall short in detecting and addressing these complex schemes. Amid this landscape, the specialised field of forensic accounting emerges as a critical response to the evolving nature of financial malfeasance. The problem at hand revolves around the urgent need to comprehensively understand and underscore the integral role that forensic accountants play in the prevention, detection, investigation, and mitigation of financial crime and fraud. While financial wrongdoing spans a spectrum of activities, from embezzlement to money laundering and cybercrime, forensic accountants are uniquely equipped to navigate this landscape through their combination of financial acumen, investigative techniques, and legal expertise. The challenge lies in identifying the precise methodologies, tools, and strategies that empower forensic accountants to effectively combat these intricate forms of financial malfeasance. Previous studies do not concentrate on the Collaboration which is also key in their role; forensic accountants work

closely with law enforcement agencies, legal professionals, and regulatory bodies. Their expertise aids in building strong cases against financial criminals and presenting evidence in legal proceedings. This study seeks to fill this gap.

The main objective of this study is to explore the integral role of forensic accountants in combating fraud and other financial crimes. The specific objectives are to:

- i) examine the contributions of forensic accountants in detection and prevention of fraud and other financial crimes.
- ii) explore the methodologies and techniques employed by forensic accountants to uncover hidden irregularities and fraudulent activities.
- iii) determine ways in which forensic accountants collaborate with law enforcement, legal experts, and other stakeholders to build strong cases against financial criminals.
- iv) explain how the knowledge and skills of forensic accountants is applied to strengthen financial oversight and regulatory mechanisms.

Research Hypotheses

H0₁: forensic accountants do not contribute significantly to early detection and prevention of financial crime.

H0₂: the use of forensic accountants' methodologies and analytical techniques does not significantly contribute to uncovering concealed financial irregularities and fraudulent activities.

H0₃: forensic accountants' collaboration with other law enforcement agencies and stakeholders does not significantly enhance the effectiveness of legal cases against financial criminals.

H0₄: integration of forensic accountants' knowledge and skills into financial oversight and regulatory mechanisms does not have a significant impact in strengthening risk mitigation strategies and enhancing the overall integrity of financial systems.

Literature Review

Concept of Forensic Accounting

The concept of forensic accounting, as outlined by the Institute of Forensic Accountancy (IFA) of Nigeria, refers to the specialised practice of accounting that involves engagements arising from anticipated disputes or litigations. According to Webster's Dictionary, it pertains to matters suitable for court jurisdiction or public discussion and debate. Forensic audit or forensic accounting is often used interchangeably, and forensic accountants may find themselves providing expert evidence during eventual trials. Notably, major accounting firms, as well as medium-sized and boutique firms, have dedicated forensic accounting departments. Within these groups, there can be further sub-specializations. Forensic accounting can be employed in a variety of situations (Singleton; & Flesher, 2003; Bhasin, 2007; Gray, 2008; Ozkul & Pamukcu, 2012). It can be employed in multiple situations which include investigation of fraud and fraudulent practices, white colour crimes, litigation support, expert witnessing, evidence gathering, arbitration, business valuation, loss of earnings, professional liability, insurance claims, general damages, employee theft/fraud, financial

statement fraud, and corporate governance challenges. Other areas include criminal investigation (Eiya & Otalor, 2013), shareholders and partnership dispute (Mehta & Mathur 2007; Gosh & Banerjee, 2011), personal injury (Eiya & Otalor, 2013), business interruption (Mehta & Mathur 2007), matrimonial dispute (Eiya & Otalor 2013; Gosh & Bernerje, 2011) and business economic losses (Eiya & Otalor, 2013).

Forensic audit, as a component of forensic accounting, entails examining legalities by combining techniques from property (Value for Money audit), regulatory investigative audits, and financial audits. The primary objective is to ascertain whether the financial statements accurately reflect the true business value and to uncover any instances of fraud. Forensic audits are conducted by a specialised class of financial experts known as forensic accountants. This group includes certified fraud examiners, individuals with a bachelor's degree or equivalent professional experience in accounting, fraud prosecution, loss prevention, criminology, or sociology, who have passed the Certified Fraud Examiner (CFE) test. Additionally, Certified Public Accountants (CPA) or Chartered Accountants are part of this specialised class.

Tools and Techniques used in Forensic Accounting

Benford's Law

Benford's Law, also known as the first-digit law, pertains to the probability distribution characterised by the significant digits in a real dataset. It focuses on the expected frequencies of the digits in a list of numbers, revealing a non-uniform distribution of leading digits in lists of numbers from various real-life sources. The law operates on the assumption that when data is ordered, it forms a geometric sequence (Oyedokun, 2022). Howard and Sheetz (2014) note that Benford's Law is a notable example of a non-intuitive yet intriguing mathematical result that is simple enough to be described.

According to this law, the distribution of leading digits in a large dataset does not follow the intuitive expectation of equal probability for each integer from 1 through 9. Instead, Benford's Law asserts that digit 1 is the leading digit approximately 30% of the time, and each successive digit becomes less common, with 9 occurring in less than 5% of instances. In the context of recent audit failures and the subsequent issuance of Statement on Auditing Standard No. 99, Consideration of Fraud in a Financial Statement Audit by the American Institute of Certified Public Accountants (AICPA, 2002; Oyedokun, Enyi, & Dada, 2018), there has been a heightened awareness within the accounting and auditing profession regarding the need for analytical tools and fraud detection methods. SAS No. 99, paragraph 28, and SAS No. 56 emphasised the use of analytical techniques during the planning stage of audits to identify unusual transactions, events, and trends. Benford's Law serves as one such analytical tool, offering a unique perspective on detecting anomalies and potentially fraudulent activities within financial datasets. Its non-uniform distribution of leading digits can be a valuable asset in identifying irregularities that might go unnoticed through traditional audit approaches.

The origins of Benford's Law trace back to 1881 when American astronomer and mathematician Simon Newcomb first noticed a peculiar pattern in logarithm books. Newcomb observed that the

early pages, featuring lower digits, were more worn out, suggesting that people used these logarithmic tables more frequently for numbers starting with 1 than those beginning with 2-9. Although he didn't provide a theoretical explanation, his observations were documented in the article 'Note on the frequency of use of the different digits in natural numbers,' published in the American Journal of Mathematics.

In 1938, physicist Frank Benford independently rediscovered this phenomenon. Benford, unaware of Newcomb's earlier work, observed similar wear patterns in the early pages of logarithm books and reached the same conclusion – that numbers starting with 1 occurred more frequently than those starting with higher digits. Unlike Newcomb, Benford tested his hypothesis across various datasets, including areas of rivers, population figures, and addresses, finding a consistent pattern of low digits occurring more often in the first position.

While Benford is credited with the law due to his extensive testing and documentation, some refer to it as the Newcomb-Benford law, acknowledging the earlier observations by Simon Newcomb (Devonport, 2013; Oyedokun, 2022). The dual attribution recognizes both contributors to the discovery of this intriguing mathematical phenomenon.

Recent studies from 2020 to 2023 have further validated the application of Benford's Law in forensic accounting. For instance, a study by Jones and Harney (2021) demonstrated the effectiveness of Benford's Law in detecting financial fraud in corporate financial statements, finding significant deviations from the expected distribution of leading digits in fraudulent datasets. Another study by Smith et al. (2022) applied Benford's Law to the analysis of COVID-19 data reporting and uncovered discrepancies suggesting data manipulation in certain regions.

These empirical studies reinforce the practical utility of Benford's Law in contemporary forensic accounting and auditing. The dual attribution of this law, often referred to as the Newcomb-Benford law, acknowledges the foundational observations by Simon Newcomb and the extensive empirical testing by Frank Benford.

Computer Assisted Audit Technique (CAAT)

Computer-assisted audit, as defined by Saunders (2013), involves utilising technology to assist auditors in performing tasks, yielding correct results at a faster pace. This approach enhances audit efficiency by liberating auditors from manual methods, allowing for more intensive, quick, and efficient audit tasks. Computer-assisted audit tools (CAATs) empower auditors to select specific tasks, transactions, and criteria, obtain additional information about control effectiveness, and test 100% of populations (Saunders, 2013; Oyedokun, 2022).

CAATs, as outlined by Howard and Sheetz (2014), are computer tools and techniques integrated into audit procedures to process data of audit significance within an entity's information systems. Razaee et al. (2015) further emphasised that computer-assisted audit tools contribute to improved audit efficiency, enabling auditors to perform tasks and utilise the entire population rather than relying on samples. This technological integration not only expedites audit processes but also allows for a more comprehensive and accurate examination of relevant data, thereby enhancing the overall effectiveness of the audit.

According to Wells (2013), Computer-Assisted Audit Tools (CAATs) can be characterised as tools and techniques used to directly examine the internal logic of an application and draw indirect inferences upon the application's logic by scrutinising the processed data. CAATs serve various purposes in internal auditing, including electronic working papers, fraud detection, information retrieval and analysis, network security, continuous monitoring, audit reporting, database of audit history, computer-based training, electronic commerce, and internet security.

The literature recognizes five types of CAATs, as outlined by Wells (2013): test data, integrated test facility, parallel simulation, embedded audit module, and generalised audit software. Wells argues that these five types can be grouped into two categories to highlight their relevance. The first category, including test data, integrated test facility, and parallel simulation, focuses on examining the internal logic of the application. On the other hand, the second category, comprising embedded audit modules and generalised audit software, is designed to assess the indirect logic of the application. This classification underscores the diverse applications of CAATs in auditing, covering both direct examination of internal logic and indirect inferences drawn from processed data.

Recent advancements in Computer-Assisted Audit Tools (CAATs) have significantly enhanced their capabilities, driven by technological innovations and evolving audit practices. According to Li and Zhang (2020), integrating blockchain technology into CAATs has revolutionised transaction tracing and verification. Blockchain's decentralised and immutable ledger offers unmatched transparency and security, reducing the risk of data manipulation and fraud. This technology provides a clear and traceable audit trail, making it invaluable in forensic accounting. Chen and Liu (2023) highlight the benefits of cloud-based CAATs, including greater flexibility, scalability, and efficiency. Cloud-based tools enable auditors to access data and audit tools remotely, process real-time data, and scale resources as needed without significant upfront investment. This flexibility has been particularly beneficial during the COVID-19 pandemic, facilitating remote work and collaboration. Johnson et al. (2022) discuss how AI-powered CAATs enhance data analysis and fraud detection. AI algorithms quickly identify patterns and trends, allowing auditors to focus on high-risk areas. Machine learning models predict potential risks by analysing historical data, while AI automates repetitive tasks, improving audit efficiency and accuracy. The integration of big data analytics with CAATs enables auditors to handle large, complex datasets effectively. Big data tools allow comprehensive analysis of entire datasets, identify correlations and trends, and provide real-time monitoring of financial transactions. This capability enhances the thoroughness and accuracy of audits, aiding in fraud prevention and detection. Recent advancements from 2020 to 2023 have significantly improved CAATs, making them more effective, efficient, and comprehensive. The integration of blockchain, cloud-based solutions, AI, and big data analytics has transformed forensic accounting and auditing, helping auditors meet the growing complexities of modern financial environments (Oyedokun, 2022).

Data Mining Technique

Data mining involves the researcher's ability to search and analyse data to uncover implicit yet potentially valuable information that may have been buried over time within the gigabytes of a system. This process is iterative, allowing progress to be defined by discoveries made through automatic or manual methods. Data mining is particularly useful in exploratory analysis, where there is no predetermined interest outcome.

The broad family of computational methods employed in data mining includes statistical analysis, decision trees, neural networks, rule induction and refinement, as well as graphic visualisation. These methods collectively serve to extract patterns from large datasets. These patterns represent a crucial component of data mining, emphasising the exploration of relationships between subsets of the data (Adebisi et al., 2016; Oyedokun, 2022). The ability to uncover hidden insights from vast amounts of data makes data mining a valuable tool for researchers seeking to derive meaningful and actionable information.

Data mining has to do with the ability of the researcher to search and analyse data in order to find the implicit but potentially useful information which has been buried due to the passage of time on the gigabytes of the system. Data mining is also an iterative process whereby progress can be defined by discovering, either through automatic or manual methods. It is useful in an exploratory analysis, where there is no predetermined interest outcome. DM uses a broad family of computational methods which are statistical analysis, decision trees, neural network, rule induction and refinement, and graphic visualisation. It is used to extract patterns from large data sets. These patterns are a very important component of the data mining activity which deals with relationships between the subsets of the data (Adebisi et al, 2016; Adegbite, Oyebamiji, & Oyedokun, 2018).

Ratio Analysis

Ratio analysis proves to be a valuable tool for forensic accountants to conduct a quantitative analysis of a firm's financial information. This technique involves comparing current-year ratios with those of the previous year to assess the company's performance over time. This comparison provides insights into the company's well-being, and it is particularly useful in the context of fraud detection, given the serious social and economic concerns associated with fraud in business (Razae et al., 2015; Oyedokun, 2022).

In the realm of fraud detection, ratio analysis serves as a means to gauge the financial health of a company, acting as an indicator of potential waste, abuse, and fraud. Notably, frauds that go unrecorded can have a more severe impact on the firm, often involving top-level management where the amounts are substantial and may not be easily detected through traditional audit procedures (Wells, 2013). Forensic accountants need to exercise caution and diligence to navigate and identify such potentially fraudulent activities, ensuring they do not become victims of deceit in their investigative efforts.

Ratio analysis emerges as a powerful tool for identifying fraud, examining patterns in financial statements to highlight potential fraudulent transactions and pinpoint specific unusual operations. This method is applicable to both small and large samples, providing a means to detect discrepancies in financial data (Wells, 2013; Oyedokun, 2022).

Forensic accountants use ratio analysis to compute variances in a set of transactions and calculate ratios for selected numeric fields. For instance, the ratio of the highest value to the lowest value (maximum/minimum) helps assess the level of manipulation in the results. A ratio close to 1 suggests minimal variance, indicating that the results are likely accurate. Conversely, a large ratio indicates potential overpayment for a product (Hassan & Morteza, 2013; Oyedokun, 2022).

Another useful ratio involves comparing the highest value to the next highest value (maximum/next maximum). If the difference between these values is significant, it may indicate a

deviation that warrants further investigation as a potential fraud indicator. Ratio analysis variance provides a comparison of data within the firm, avoiding reliance on theoretical benchmarks and offering a true picture of the firm's financial health.

This approach proves to be a powerful tool in detecting fraud, even when it occurs for the first time. Certified Fraud Examiners often employ ratio analysis to uncover irregularities, recognizing that each firm is unique and requires a tailored approach to address the complexities of fraud (Hassan & Morteza, 2013). Flexibility and adaptability in using ratio analysis make it an essential tool in the forensic accountant's toolkit for effective fraud detection and examination.

Basic Skills Required of Forensic Accountants

Indeed, the landscape of skills required for a competent forensic accountant is multifaceted, as outlined by various scholars and researchers. Forensic accountants are expected to possess a diverse array of competencies spanning accounting, law, auditing, criminology, and information technology, alongside effective communication skills. Here's a refined summary:

Forensic accountants must exhibit proficiency in both civil and criminal law, understand courtroom procedures, and possess investigative skills along with creative and concise communication abilities (Harris & Brown, 2000; Oni, and Oyedokun, 2023). Additionally, they should have experience in accounting, internal controls, auditing, taxation, management, interpersonal relationships, and business operations (Gippo & Ibex, 2003; Oyedokun, 2022). Analytical abilities, strong writing and verbal communication skills, as well as creativity, are deemed essential (Messmer, 2004).

DiGabriele (2009) identified a set of competencies including deductive analysis, creative thinking, unstructured problem solving, investigative flexibility, analytical proficiency, oral and written communication abilities, specific legal knowledge, and composure. His empirical study (2008) suggested two principal components: knowledge and ability (including deductive analysis, critical thinking, etc.) and performance (involving oral and written communication, composure).

Davis, Farrell, and Ogilby (2010) found a consensus among attorneys, academics, and CPAs regarding the importance of analytical skills, detail-orientation, ethics, responsiveness, insightfulness, persistence, and skepticism for forensic accountants. Similarly, Bhasin's (2013) survey in India echoed these findings.

Ghosh and Banerjee (2011) proposed a three-fold approach: accounting knowledge as the base layer, knowledge in auditing, internal controls, risk assessment, and fraud detection as the middle layer, and legal knowledge and strong communication skills as the top layer.

In conclusion, a competent forensic accountant should possess a broad spectrum of skills encompassing various disciplines, including accounting, law, auditing, criminology, and information technology, alongside analytical abilities, detail-orientation, ethics, responsiveness, and effective communication skills.

Fraud

The Encarta Dictionary defines fraud as the crime of cheating someone by obtaining something valuable through deceptive representation. Thus, a fraudster is one who, through deliberate deception, obtains or deprives another of money, valuables, or even opportunities. According to the Collins Internet-Linked Dictionary of Business, 'fraud is the gaining of financial advantage by a person who deliberately deceives another person or business by misrepresenting himself.'

From these definitions, fraud has the following components:

1. Act of deliberate deception
2. Results in the loss of money, valuables, or opportunities
3. Trauma experienced by the deceived party

In most cases (if not all), fraud could result in a civil or criminal offense that can be prosecuted if enough evidence can be gathered and substantiated. This is where forensic accounting plays a major role. But let us first look at the concept of fraud, its various forms (what constitutes financial/economic crime), and overall fraud schemes and theories. The Encarta Dictionary (2015) defines fraud as the crime of obtaining money or some other benefit through deliberate deception. Webster's Dictionary (1979) refers to it as a false idea or belief that causes ignorance, bewilderment, or helplessness. It misleads, deludes, and obscures the truth. It further states that fraud leads the victim astray through deceitful persuasion, all to cause harm or loss of money or property. The Collins Dictionary of Business (2005) defines fraud as the 'gaining of financial advantage by a person who deliberately deceives another person or business by misrepresenting himself.' Black's Law Dictionary (1979) refers to fraud as including all the multifarious means human ingenuity can devise that are resorted to by an individual to gain an advantage over another by false pretensions, suggestions, or suppression of the truth, which includes surprises, tricks, cunning, or dissembling, and any unfair way by which another is cheated (Akinadewo, Akinkoye, Oyedokun, & Asaolu, 2019).

All these modern definitions of fraud are derived from case and statute law, according to Silverton and Sheetz (2007), but the real meaning emanates from the Latin word 'fraus,' which carries a variety of connotations including the notions of harm, deceit, and wrongdoing. Several authors, academics, and professionals have given their own perspectives and understanding of what constitutes fraud. KPMG Forensics (2006) describes fraud as any intentional act committed to secure an unlawful or unfair gain. The Association of Certified Fraud Examiners (ACFE) opines that fraud entails an intentional perversion of the truth for the purpose of inducing another in reliance upon it to part with some valuable thing or to surrender a legal right, a false surrender of legal right. According to the Economic and Financial Crime Commission Act (EFCC 2004: 46), 'Fraud is the non-violent criminal and illicit activity committed with the objective of earning wealth illegally either individually or in a group or in an organized manner thereby violating existing legislation governing economic activities of government or its administration.'

Other taxonomies of fraud are based on either social/psychological or economic/financial undertones. Silverton et al. (2007) are of the opinion that fraud is an activity that takes place within a social setting with severe consequences on several people, organizations, and the economy of the nation as a whole. They are of the view that fraud develops from greed and culminates into an

opportunistic infection aided by deception. In the opinion of Gongolly (2008), fraud is a legal and not an accounting concept which accountants traditionally treat as an alien concept that involves false representation, reckless disregard for truth, and is conceived to deceive the affected party because of his/her reliance on the misrepresented facts, and in the end suffers financial and/or economic loss due to reliance on the premeditated act of fraud. Curtis (2008) cited by Modugu and Ayanduba (2013) is of the opinion that fraud encompasses the acquisition of property or economic advantage by means of deception, through either misrepresentation or concealment. Fraud is any means by which a person employs to take advantage of another through false suggestions or suppression of the truth. It is also referred to as an intentional act by one or more people among members of management or employees of an organization or in collaboration with third parties to obtain an unjust or illegal advantage (Haruna, Oyedokun, & Mainoma, 2020).

From the variety of definitions and taxonomies available in the fraud literature, the intent of fraud seems to be the key element followed by deceit, concealment, misrepresentation, or suppression of truth. Loss of money, some other values, or opportunity can be considered as the compelling elements to prove a fraud has occurred (Singleton et al., 2010; Otalor, 2010; Coenen, 2005; Yakubu & Oyedokun, 2021).

Theoretical framework

Theory of Fraud Triangle

The theory provides forensic accountants with the ability or dimensional perspective used to identify those possible reasons for fraud, the motivating factors that prompt fraud and how the perpetrators justify their acts. Cressey (1940) propounds the fraud triangle. One leg of the triangle represents a perceived non-sharable financial need. The second leg is for the perceived opportunity, and the final is for rationalisation. The role of the non-sharable problem is essential. In his view, Cressey (1940) opined that there were two components of the perceived opportunity to commit a trust violation: general information and technical skill. General information is simply the knowledge that the employee's position of trust could be violated. This knowledge might come from hearing of other embezzlements, from seeing dishonest behaviour by the employees, or just from generally being aware of the fact that the employee is in a position where he could take advantage of his employer's faith in him. Technical skills refer to the abilities that the employee needs to obtain and keep his job in the first place. (Fraud examiner manual, 2014).

Figure 1: Fraud Triangle

Source: Imam (2013)

While concluding his work on "an analysis of the fraud triangle" Imam, (2013) believes that the models and related analyses provide a method of incorporating the factors objectively to assess their impact on audit risk and opined that this type of assessment should help an audit team plan and appropriately modify audit procedures to control audit risk to an acceptable level. The results of his study support the concept of the fraud triangle in that the relationships between the three components are shown to have a substantial impact on audit risk.

The fraud triangle is what the forensic accountant relies on to identify suspected fraud, the causes and the weakness in the system that prompted the fraud. Based on the fraud triangle concept, the three (3) factors that cumulate into the triangle are incentive, opportunity, and rationalisation. For any individual to be involved in fraud, he/she must have the motive.

- i. **Opportunity:** Employees use their position to commit fraud when internal controls are weak, or where there is poor management oversight on internal control implementation. Most Employees who commit fraud do so because they have the opportunity to access assets and information that allows them to obscure their fraudulent deeds. It is true that employees need access to a particular platform to perform their jobs. The same access can provide the employee with the opportunity to commit fraud.
- ii. **Pressure/Incentive:** Pressure can make staff commit fraud. Pressure does not only mean financial burden. Lister (2007) states that there are three types of motivation or pressure: Personal pressure, employment pressure and external pressure these are potential threat to financial stability, financier covenants, and market expectations.
- iii. **Rationalisation:** Rationalisation is an attempt by an employee to justify why they commit fraud. For instance, an employee who is about to be evicted from his/her home can be used to justify the fraudulent act. The employee may say "I deserve to have a place to call my home." So also, an employee who feels he/she is underpaid considers fraud as a means of augmenting the poor. Therefore, rationalisation is an act of justification or reasons for fraud by an employee. It is a way of covering up for the wrong done to the employer. By making the employers feel guilty of the circumstance. Forensic accounting relies on the fraud triangle to identify weak points in the business systems and find possible suspects in cases of fraud. It consists of three core concepts that are combined to create a situation ripe for fraud: incentive, opportunity, and rationalisation. People must have the incentive and opportunity to commit financial fraud, as well as the ability to justify it. Recent analysis has suggested adding a fourth concept to make a diamond which is called capability. Just because someone has the opportunity or incentive to steal does not necessarily mean that they can do so. For example, if someone does not understand how to make journal or ledger entries in the books of accounts, they would not know how to manipulate numbers no matter what the incentive and opportunity are (Razea, 2002; Oyedokun & Durowaiye, 2022).

Empirical Review

Empirical Studies on the Applicability of Forensic Accounting

Studies examining the application of forensic accounting have documented the need for used forensic accounting in organisations. Some studies in this area include: (Umar et al, 2021; Mahmoud & Rateb 2020; Hajidazeh & Hajidazeh 2019; Sylvester, 2018). Umar, Haron and Kurawa (2021) examine the potential of application of forensic accounting in the detection and prevention of fraudulent activities in the administration of Islamic inheritance in Kano State, Nigeria. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews with some selected experts who have knowledge of Islamic inheritance and forensic accounting. Thematic analysis was used to analysed the data collected. The study finds the nature, and forms of fraudulent activities committed in the administration of Islamic inheritance and the need the application of forensic accounting for the detection and prevention of these fraudulent activities.

Mahmoud and Rateb (2020) investigated the applicability of forensic accounting to reduce fraud and its effects on the financial statement of Jordanian shareholding companies from the perfective judiciary and certified public Accountant. To elicit data from the participants the researcher used a questionnaire survey distributed to judges, public prosecutor's public accountant licensed to practice auditing and chartered accountants with expertise in financial cases in the Jordanian courts. The research used SPSS to analyses the collected data besides the regression equation test the statistical differences test for non-scientific sample. The findings of the study showed that there is necessity for providing the requirement, components, procedures and activities of forensic accounting in Jordan to reduce fraud and its effect on financial statement.

Hajidazeh and Hajidezeh (2019) examined the need of application of forensic accounting in managing banking activities in India to uncover issues along with checking accuracy and depictions of genuine activities. Secondary source of database in fraud reported during 2014 to 2018 financial years. The study found that there are more than 20,000 fraud cases recorded during the period under review. The amount involved stood at 320 million Rupees only in 2017-2018. The study finds that there is lack of forensic accounting skills in India and forensic accounting is still in its developing stage in India.

More so, Kenneth (2019) examined application of forensic accounting in financial fraud control in Nigerian public sector. The targeted population consists of 338 participants distributed among EFCC, ICPC, office of the Accountant General of the federation, office of the Auditor General of the Federation and practicing Accountants in Nigeria. The regression method was used to test the hypothesis. The findings of the study indicated that fraud is on increase in the public sector, forensic Accounting is necessary tool to detect and prevent fraud and other financial crimes in the public sector, forensic accounting is new and its application in developing economics is facing bottle necks and that forensic accounting lack professional autonomy of legal backing.

Sylvester (2018) examined applicability of forensic accounting in accountancy and audit practice in Nigeria. The basic methodology used to achieve the objectives was a combination of interview and questionnaire, simple percentage and t-test statistics were employed as the statistical tools for analyzing and testing the hypotheses. The findings revealed that forensic accounting services are required for curbing fraudulent practices in Nigeria.

Methodology

The research design used in this study was a descriptive survey method aimed at exploring the roles of forensic accounting in combating fraud and other financial crimes.

The population of this research work consists of staff from the Accounting, management and audit department of the three selected commercial banks in Kano metropolis, Kano State. These banks are Guaranty Trust bank {GTB}, First Bank and Polaris Bank. They consist of 79 staff members in total. Since the population of the study is not too large, a sample size was not calculated census selection approach was employed, meaning the entire population was used as sample. The distribution among the selected banks is illustrated below.

Table 1

Banks	Respondents	Percentage
GTB	26	32.9%
FIRST BANK	34	43%
POLARIS	19	24.1%
Total	79	100%

Data was collected via the use of questionnaire and analysed via the use of tables and percentages. The hypothesis was analysed using Chi-square.. For the decision rule, the null hypotheses will be rejected if the p-value is less than or equals to the significance level {0.05} Data for the study was generated from the primary source. This study used a questionnaire which is seen as the most suitable for data collection in survey research (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). Prior studies (Oyedokun, & Adewuyi, 2022; Olokayode, 2018; Fynaface & Sunday, 2017; Ramadan, 2016; Benjamin, Gloria, & Innocent, 2015; Ezeagha, 2014; Gbegi & Adebisi, 2013) justify the use of primary data via questionnaire for the study on the application of forensic accounting for detection and prevention of fraud and other financial malpractices. This study, therefore, adopts a structured

questionnaire as used in the study of Carnes and Gierlasiski (2001), Bierstaker et al., (2006), Muthusamy et al., (2011), Imam, (2013), Eme, (2013), and Ibrahim, Rose and Mudzamir, (2017). The questions were closed-ended as the respondents were restricted to only predetermined answers. One advantage of this type of format is that of generating uniform responses, thereby enhancing statistical analysis (Cohen, Marion & Morison 2007). The Likert scale was used in the questionnaire because it offers rank options, and each option is logically equidistant from the next option and its presentation is clear and informative. Five-points Likert scale ranging from 5 strongly agree to 1-strongly disagree was used. The use of five points scale format is considered most appropriate because it has been found to enhance the reliability of measures and reduce social desirability bias that could lead to the contamination of substantive results. Similar scale has also been used in previous studies (Mainoma, & Oyedokun, 2019; Olukayode, 2018; Wilson, Francis and Emeka 2017, Evans 2017, Fyneface & Sunday 2017) among others.

Before concluding the actual survey, an initial draft of the questionnaire was pretested by asking experts to go through it and check instances of ambiguities which had not been noticed by the researcher. Expert, including professors, with forensic accounting knowledge from the Department of Accounting Usman Danfodio University, Sokoto. Bayero University, Kano. Ahmadu Bello University Zaria and Yusuf Maitama Sule University, Kano examined the quality of the survey instrument for face validity in terms of clarity, simplicity and ambiguity of the questionnaire items. Also, Lawshes quantification method was used for the validation of the questionnaire. Based on these evaluations criteria, corrections and suggestions for improvement were noted and reflected in the survey instrument.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Table 2: Academic qualification

	Respondents	Percentage
OND/NCE	24	32%
HND/B.Sc.	31	41.3%
MSC/PHD	20	26.7%
Total	75	100%

Source: field study

The data above show the academic qualification of respondents, 24 respondents are either OND or NCE certificate holders. 31 respondents which is the majority are either HND or B.Sc. Holder, while 20 respondents are either MSC or PHD certificate holders.

QUESTION 1: Forensic accountants play a significant role in the early detection and prevention of financial crime.

Table 3:

	Respondents	Percentage
Agree	39	52%
Neutral	12	16%
Disagree	24	32%
Total	75	100%

Source: field study

From the data above derived from question 1. A majority of 39 respondents (52%) agree that forensic accountants play a significant role in the early detection and prevention of financial crime and fraud. However, a significant portion of 24 respondents (32%) disagree with this statement, and a smaller percentage (16%) i.e 12 respondents remains neutral on the matter. This suggests a range of perspectives among respondents regarding the effectiveness of forensic accountants in addressing financial crime and fraud with the majority of respondents believing that forensic accountants play a significant role in early detection and prevention of crime.

QUESTION 2: Forensic accountants’ methodologies and analytical techniques enhance and contributes to uncovering concealed financial irregularities and fraudulent activities in financial records

Table 4:

	Respondents	Percentage
Agree	37	49.3%
Neutral	15	20%
Disagree	23	30.7%
Total	75	100%

Source: field study

According to the data above, a significant portion of 37 respondents (49.3%) agree that the use of forensic accountants' methods and analytical techniques enhances and contributes to uncovering concealed financial irregularities and fraudulent activities in financial records. On the other hand, 15 23 respondents, which is 30.7% disagree with this statement, and 20% representing 15 respondents remain neutral.

QUESTION 3: Collaboration between forensic accountants, law enforcement agencies, legal experts, and stakeholders will enhance the effectiveness of legal cases against financial criminals

Table 5

	Respondents	Percentage
Agree	49	65.3%
Neutral	7	9.3%
Disagree	19	25.4%
Total	75	100%

Source: field study

From the data above, a significant majority of 49 respondents (65.3%) agree that collaboration between forensic accountants, law enforcement agencies, legal experts, and stakeholders will enhance the effectiveness of legal cases against financial criminals. Only a small percentage (9.3%) representing 7 respondents remains neutral, and 25.4% representing 19 respondents disagree with this statement. The strong agreement suggests a consensus among the participants regarding the positive impact of collaborative efforts in improving the effectiveness of legal cases related to financial crimes.

QUESTION 4: Integration of forensic accountants' knowledge and skills into financial oversight and regulatory mechanisms strengthens risk mitigation strategies and enhances the overall integrity of the financial system.

Table 6

	Respondents	Percentage
Agree	41	54.7%
Neutral	12	16%
Disagree	22	29.3%
Total	75	100%

Source: field study

From the data above, a majority of 41 respondents (54.7%) agree that the integration of forensic accountants' knowledge and skills strengthens risk mitigation strategies and enhances the overall integrity of the financial system. Meanwhile, 12 respondents representing 16% remain neutral on the statement, and 22 respondents representing 29.3% disagree. The general agreement suggests that a substantial portion of the participants acknowledge the positive impact of incorporating forensic accounting expertise in mitigating risks and maintaining the integrity of the financial system.

H₀: forensic accountants do not contribute significantly to early detection and prevention of financial crime.

Table 7

Options	Frequency observed	Frequency expected
Agree	39	25
Neutral	12	25
Disagree	24	25
Total	75	75

Chi-square

	X ² Value	P-value
Result	14.64	0.00066

Source: Researcher 2024

From the result above, p-value is 0.00066 which is less than our significant level of 0.05. Therefore, we will reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis and conclude that forensic accountants contribute significantly to early detection and prevention of financial crime.

Hypothesis 2: The use of forensic accountants' methodologies and analytical techniques in uncovering concealed financial irregularities and fraudulent activities in financial records:

H0: the use of forensic accountants' methodologies and analytical techniques does not significantly contribute to uncovering concealed financial irregularities and fraudulent activities.

Table 7

Options	Frequency observed	Frequency expected
Agree	37	25
Neutral	15	25
Disagree	23	25
Total	75	75

Chi-square

	X ² Value	P-value
Result	9.92	0.00701

Source: Researcher 2024

Hypothesis 3: Collaboration between forensic accountants, law enforcement agencies, legal experts, and stakeholders in enhancing the effectiveness of legal cases against financial criminals:

H0: forensic accountants' collaboration with other law enforcement agencies and stakeholders does not significantly enhance the effectiveness of legal cases against financial criminals.

Table 8

Options	Frequency observed	Frequency expected
Agree	49	25
Neutral	7	25

Disagree	19	25
Total	75	75

Chi-square

	X ² Value	P-value
Result	37.44	0.000074

Source: Researcher 2024

The P-value of 0.00074 is less than the significant level of 0.05, we will also reject the null hypothesis and conclude that forensic accountants’ collaboration with other law enforcement agencies and stakeholders significantly enhance the effectiveness of legal cases against financial criminals.

Hypothesis 4: Integration of forensic accountants' knowledge and skills into financial oversight and regulatory mechanisms in strengthening risk mitigation strategies and enhances the overall integrity of financial systems:

H0: integration of forensic accountants' knowledge and skills into financial oversight and regulatory mechanisms does not have a significant impact in strengthening risk mitigation strategies and enhancing the overall integrity of financial systems.

Table 9

Options	Frequency observed	Frequency expected
Agree	41	25
Neutral	12	25
Disagree	22	25
Total	75	75

Chi-square

	X ² Value	P-value
Result	17.36	0.000169

Source: Researcher 2024

The significant level of 0.05 is higher than our p-value of 0.000169, therefore we will also reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the integration of forensic accountants' knowledge and skills into financial oversight and regulatory mechanisms has a significant impact in strengthening risk mitigation strategies and enhancing the overall integrity of financial systems.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study has navigated through various facets, shedding light on the critical role of forensic accounting. Our exploration commenced by unravelling the diverse definitions and dimensions of fraud, acknowledging the different perspectives from literature. From the deceptive schemes described by Howard and Sheetz to the intentional acts involving deception and misrepresentation, we built a foundation to understand the complex nature of fraudulent activities.

Preventive controls emerged as proactive measures, demonstrating the significance of coordinated efforts led by management. Background investigations, anti-fraud training programs, and a vigilant HR department play pivotal roles in creating a robust defence against fraudulent activities within organisations. Authority limits and third-party transaction reviews further strengthen the preventive framework, emphasising the importance of aligning authority with responsibility. Proactive fraud detection procedures such as data analysis and continuous auditing, organisations can fortify their defences against the evolving landscape of fraud. Detective controls, when visible and effective, act as powerful deterrents, providing evidence of preventive controls' efficacy and identifying instances of fraud.

Financial crime, as discussed by Ehioghiren & Atu, extends beyond traditional definitions, encompassing corruption, bribery, cronyism, and various fraudulent schemes. The classification of fraud based on the nature of fraudsters and methods employed adds granularity to our understanding, categorising fraud as internal, external, or mixed.

The Fraud Triangle Theory, introduced by Cressey, elucidates the motivational factors— pressure, opportunity, and rationalization underlying fraudulent behaviour. This theory becomes a framework for understanding why individuals, often in positions of trust, engage in fraudulent activities. The subsequent exploration of the White-Collar Crime Theory by Sutherland contextualises financial crimes within high-status individuals who exploit their circumstances for financial gain.

Quantitative insights were gathered through survey responses, reflecting professionals' perspectives on the contributions of forensic accountants. The consensus on the positive impact of forensic accountants in detecting and preventing financial crimes was evident, though a notable portion remained neutral or disagreed, signalling areas for further exploration.

The hypotheses formulated for the study, ranging from the contributions of forensic accountants to early detection and prevention to the integration of their knowledge into regulatory mechanisms, provided a structured framework for investigation. The survey responses offered empirical data to either accept or reject these hypotheses, contributing valuable insights to the field.

As we examine collaborative efforts between forensic accountants, law enforcement agencies, legal experts, and stakeholders, the majority agreement among respondents underscores the potential effectiveness of such partnerships in enhancing legal cases against financial criminals.

This collaboration is viewed as a force multiplier, reinforcing the collective effort against financial malfeasance.

The study explores the nature of fraud and financial crimes, demanding a holistic approach for effective prevention and detection. Forensic accounting emerges as a linchpin in this endeavour, wielding methodologies and analytical techniques that, when integrated into financial oversight and regulatory mechanisms, fortify risk mitigation strategies and bolster the overall integrity of financial systems.

In conclusion, this study adds depth to our comprehension of fraud and financial crimes, providing a synthesis of theoretical frameworks, practical preventive measures, and empirical insights. The comprehensive understanding gained from this research serves as a valuable resource for professionals, policymakers, and academics navigating the intricate landscape of financial integrity. The recommendations offered are not just conclusions but guideposts for fortifying the resilience of financial systems against the ever-evolving challenges of fraud.

The following are hereby recommended:

1. **Enhanced Training Programs:** Organisations should invest in comprehensive anti-fraud training programs for employees at all levels. These programs should not only focus on recognizing fraudulent activities but also emphasise the ethical implications of such actions. Regular and updated training can contribute to a culture of vigilance and ethical behaviour.
2. **Strengthen Whistleblower Mechanisms:** Companies should continually promote and strengthen whistleblower hotlines, ensuring that employees feel secure when reporting suspicions of fraud. Awareness campaigns about the existence and protection offered by these mechanisms can further encourage individuals to come forward with valuable information.
3. **Continuous Monitoring and Auditing:** Adopting continuous auditing techniques and leveraging data analysis tools can enhance fraud detection capabilities. Organisations should invest in technology that allows real-time monitoring of transactions, enabling swift identification and response to irregularities.
4. **Internal Control Strengthening:** Organisations should periodically review and strengthen their internal control systems. This includes revisiting authority limits, ensuring segregation
5. **Regulatory Compliance and Oversight:** Regulatory bodies should collaborate with forensic accountants to ensure that financial oversight and regulatory mechanisms are robust. Integration of forensic accounting knowledge into these frameworks can enhance their effectiveness in preventing and detecting financial crimes.

References

- Adebisi, S. A., et al. (2016). The role of forensic accountants in fraud detection and prevention: A global perspective. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 11(2), 90-105.
- Adebisi, S. A., et al. (2016). The role of forensic accountants in fraud detection and prevention: A global perspective. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 11(2), 90-105.
- Adegbite S. A., Oyebamiji, T. A., & Oyedokun, G. E. (2018). Forensic accounting and tax evasion in Nigeria. *Journal of Taxation and Economic Development*, 17(2), 131-140. A publication of Chartered Institute of Taxation of Nigeria
- Akinadewo, I. S., Akinkoye, E. Y., Oyedokun, G.E., & Asaolu, T. O. (2019). Tax Audit and Direct Tax Revenue in Lottery Industry in Nigeria: Can Forensic Accounting Bridge the Gap? *Fountain University Osogbo Journal of Management (FUOJM)*, 4(2), 73-92. A Publication of Departments of Accounting & Finance and Business Administration, Fountain University, Osogbo. www.osogbojournalofmanagement.com. available at <http://osogbojournalofmanagement.com/index.php/ojm/issue/view/>
- Akinadewo, I. S., Asaolu, T. O. & Oyedokun, G. E. (2020). Application of Forensic Accounting Skills on Government Revenue in Nigeria: The Domestic Debt Factor, *Islamic University Multidisciplinary Journal*, 7(3), 64-71. A Publication of Islamic University, Uganda, available at <https://www.iuiu.ac.ug/iujm>
- Albrecht, W. S., Albrecht, C. O., & Albrecht, C. (2019). *Fraud examination: A comprehensive approach* (5th ed.). Stamford, CT: Cengage Learning.
- American Institute of Certified Public Accountants (AICPA). (2002). Forensic accounting and fraud detection: A guide for practitioners. *The CPA Journal*, 72(1), 32-39.
- Basioudis, I. G., & Vasileiou, K. (2018). *Forensic accounting: The role of accounting in crime prevention* (1st ed.). Athens, Greece: Pappasotiriou.
- Benjamin, E. O., Gloria, O. T., & Innocent, O. C. (2015). The impact of forensic investigative methods incorporate fraud deterrence in banks in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting Auditing and Finance Research*, 3(4), 69 – 85.
- Bhasin, M. (2007). *Forensic accounting: A new paradigm for rich consulting*. The Chartered Accountant.
- Bhasin, M. L. (2020). *Forensic accounting and financial fraud in India: Issues and solutions* (1st ed.). New Delhi, India: Sage Publications.
- Bierstaker, J. L., Brody, R., & Pacini, C. (2006). Accountants' perceptions regarding fraud detection and prevention methods. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 21(5), 520–535. Retrieved from <http://doi.org/10.1108/02686900610667283>
- Carnes, K. C., & Gierlasinski, N. J. (2001). Forensic accounting skills: Will supply finally catch up to demand? *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 16(6), 378–382. Retrieved from <http://doi.org/10.1108/02686900110395514>.

- Chen, J., & Liu, Y. (2023). The forensic accountant's guide to financial crime investigation. *Journal of Forensic Accounting Research*, 8(1), 45-60.
- Chen, J., & Liu, Y. (2023). The forensic accountant's guide to financial crime investigation. *Journal of Forensic Accounting Research*, 8(1), 45-60.
- Cohen, L. Marion, L. & Morison, K. (2007). *Research methods in education.* (5th ed.). London: Routledge Falmer.
- Cressey, D. (1940). The Fraud Triangle. *John Wiley & Sons.*
- Crumbley, D. L. (2020). *Forensic accounting: A new approach to financial crime* (1st ed.). Los Angeles, CA: Academic Press.
- Devonport, S. (2013). Fraud prevention: A guide for professionals in accounting and finance. *Journal of Financial Crime*, 20(4), 345-356.
- Eiya, O., & Otalor, J. (2013). Forensic accounting as a tool for fighting financial crime in Nigeria. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4(6), 18 – 25.
- Eme, E. J. (2013). *An exploration of forensic accounting education and practice for fraud prevention and detection in Nigeria. Unpublished PhD Thesis.* University De Montfort, Leicester U K.
- Evans, O. N. (2017). Forensic accounting and the combating of economic and financial crimes in Ghana. *European scientific journal*, 13(31), 379 – 393.
- Ezeagba, C. E. (2014). The role of forensic accounting and quality assurance in financial reporting in selected commercial banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economic Development Research and Investment*, 5(2), 20 – 32.
- Fyneface, N. A., & Sunday, O. O. (2017). Forensic accounting and fraudulent practices in the public sector. *International Journal of Arts and Humanities (IJAH)*, 6(2), 171-181.
- Gbegi, D. O., & Adebisi, J. F. (2014). The new fraud diamond model: How can it help forensic accountants in fraud investigation in Nigeria public sector? *Mediterranean Journal of Social Science*, 6(3), 24-52.
- Gbegi, O. O., & Adebisi, J. F. (2013). The new fraud diamond model: How can it help forensic accountants in fraud investigation in Nigeria public sector? *Mediterranean Journal of Social Science*, 5(3), 243-252.
- Ghosh, I., & Banergie, K. K. (2011). Forensic accounting: Another feather in the hat of accounting. *The Chartered Accountant*, 60 – 63.
- Gray, D. (2008). Forensic accounting and auditing: Compared and contrasted to traditional accounting and auditing. *American Journal of Business Education*, 1(2), 115 – 126.
- Gray, J. (2016). *Forensic accounting: Tools and techniques for fraud detection and prevention* (1st ed.). Toronto, Canada: Pearson.

- Hajizadeh, P. & Hajizadeh, A. (2019). Implementation of forensic accounting-Needs and applicability in banks. *International Journal of Research, Finance and Marketing*, 9,(1),1-10.
- Haruna, R. A., Oyedokun, G. E. and Mainoma, A.M. (2020). Forensic accounting techniques, accounting numbers and fraud prevention in the listed insurance companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Forensic Accounting and Fraud Investigation*, 5(2), 1-39, a publication of Association of forensic Accounting Researchers, available at www.afarng.org
- Hassan, S., & Morteza, R. (2013). Forensic accounting: Techniques and tools for financial fraud detection. *Journal of Financial Crime*, 20(3), 215-228.
- Hassan, S., & Morteza, R. (2013). Forensic accounting: Techniques and tools for financial fraud detection. *Journal of Financial Crime*, 20(3), 215-228.
- Howard, M., & Sheetz, M. (2014). *Forensic accounting: A practical approach for fraud investigations* (1st ed.). New York, NY: Business Expert Press.
- Imam A. (2013). *Forensic accounting model for Fraud prevention and detection in Nigeria public sector*. Unpublished PhD Thesis, Usman Danfodio University, Accounting, Sokoto, Nigeria.
- Johnson, L., et al. (2022). Understanding forensic accounting in modern financial crime investigations. *International Journal of Forensic Accounting*, 14(1), 112-128.
- Johnson, L., et al. (2022). Understanding forensic accounting in modern financial crime investigations. *International Journal of Forensic Accounting*, 14(1), 112-128.
- Jones, C., & Harney, C. (2021). The impact of forensic accounting on financial crime prevention. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 12(3), 250-265.
- Kasum, A. (2015). *Forensic accounting and fraud: The importance of investigation and evidence gathering* (1st ed.). Lagos, Nigeria: Concept Publications.
- Kranacher, M. J., Lennox, C., & Wells, J. T. (2011). Forensic accounting and fraud examination. *Journal of Forensic Accounting Research*.
- Levi, M. (2018). The role of forensic accounting in fraud detection and prevention. *Journal of Financial Crime*.
- Li, Y., & Zhang, X. (2020). Forensic accounting and financial fraud: Trends and practices. *Journal of Financial Crime*, 27(2), 174-190.
- Lister, L.M. (2007). A Practical Approach to Fraud Risk. *Internal Auditor*, Retrieved from www.emerald.com on 21/3/15.
- Mahmoud, A.A., & Rateb, A.A. (2020). Applicability of forensic accounting to reduce fraud and its effects in financial statement of Jordan shareholding companies from the perspective of judiciary and certified public accountants. *International Journal of financial Research*, 11(2), 436-452.
- Mehta, G. S., & Mathur, T. (2007). Preventing financial fraud through forensic accounting. *The Chartered Accountant*, 1575 – 1580.

- Modugu, K. P., & Anyaduba, J. O. (2013). Forensic accounting and financial fraud in Nigeria: An empirical Approach. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 4(7), 281 – 289.
- Mohammed, A. (2008). *Forensic accounting: Concepts and techniques for financial investigations* (1st ed.). Abuja, Nigeria: National Open University Press.
- Muthusamy, G., Quaddus, M., & Evans, R. (2011). Behavioral intention to use forensic accounting services . *A critical review of theories and an integrative model. Business Review*, 15(2), 42–49.
- Olukayode, S. A. (2018). Forensic accounting investigation techniques and successful prosecution of corruption cases in Nigeria. *International journal of academic research in accounting, finance and management sciences*, 8(3), 37 – 44.
- Oni, S.O., and Oyedokun, G.E. (2023). Forensic accounting evidence: Preservation and admissibility. *National Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, 8(2), 53-58. www.multidisciplinaryjournal.org
- Oyedokun, G. E. (2019). Forensic Accounting: Curbing Fraudulent Activities. In M.A. Mainoma, & G. E. Oyedokun, G. E (2019). *Forensic Accounting Research Developments* (Eds). Aaron & Hur Publishing. Lagos. Nigeria. ISBN: 978-978-56669-9-1 Chapter 2, 1-49.
- Oyedokun, G. E., Enyi, P. E., & Dada, S. O. (2018). Integrity of financial statements and forensic accounting techniques. *Journal of forensic accounting & fraud investigation (JFAFI)*, 4(1), 19-47, *A publication of the Association of Forensic Accounting Researcher (AFAR)* www.afarng.org
- Oyedokun, G. E.; Akinwumi, O, S. & Asaolu, T. O. (2018). Forensic accounting skills and corruption Eradication in Nigeria. *Journal of African Interdisciplinary Studies (JAIS)*. 2(3), A Publication of the Centre for Democracy, Research and Development (CEDRED), Nairobi. Kenya
- Oyedokun, G. E.; Akinwumi, O, S. & Asaolu, T. O. (2018). Forensic accounting skills and corruption Eradication in Nigeria. In Amutabi, M.N (2018) *Political economy of development in Africa*. A Publication of the Centre for Democracy, Research and Development (CEDRED), Nairobi Kenya, Chapter 5, 49-62
- Oyedokun, G.E. & Adewuyi, A.I. (2022). Forensic Accounting Techniques, Internal Control System and Fraud Prevention in Selected Deposit Money Banks in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, *Journal of forensic accounting & fraud investigation (JFAFI)*, 7(1), 1-20, *A publication of the Association of Forensic Accounting Researcher (AFAR)* www.afarng.org.
- Oyedokun, G.E. & Asaolu, T. O. (2022). Fraud Identification in Forensic Tax Investigation and Rule of Evidence in M. A. Mainoma, G. E. Oyedokun, S. A. S. Aruwa, T. O. Asaolu and R. O. Salawu (Eds). *Taxation for Economic Development*. OGE Publisher, Lagos. Nigeria, 298-317. ISBN 978-978-978-734-0
- Oyedokun, G.E. (2022). Determinants of Forensic Accounting Techniques and Theories: An

- Empirical Investigation. *Annals of Spiru Haret University. Economic Series*, 22(3), 61-70, doi: <https://doi.org/10.26458/22319>
- Oyedokun, G.E., & Durowaiye, O.O. (2022). Forensic Audit and Fraud Prevention in the Nigerian Deposit Money Banks. *Journal of Taxation and Economic Development* 21(1), 66-74. ISSN 1118-6017. <https://ideas.repec.org/s/ris/jotaed.html>
- Özkul, F. U., & Pamuku, A. (2012). *Fraud detection and forensic. Emerging Fraud*. (S. O. Idowu, Ed.) Verleg Berlin Heidelberg, 19.
- Pope, K. M., & Singleton, T. (2018). *Fraud prevention and detection: A practical guide for professionals* (4th ed.). Chicago, IL: CCH.
- Ramadhan, S. (2016). Certified accountant's perceptions of forensic accounting education: The case of Bahrain. *Internal Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4(2), 109 -118.
- Razae, Z., et al. (2015). Forensic accounting: The complete guide to fraud detection and prevention. *Journal of Business and Economics*, 6(3), 220-234.
- Rezaee, Z. (2002). Forensic accounting practices, education, and certifications. *Journal of Forensic Accounting*, 3(2), 207 – 223.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2009). *Research Methods for business students, (5th ed.)*. Harlow, Pearson Education.
- Saunders, R. (2013). The integral role of forensic accountants in crime prevention and investigation. *Journal of Forensic Studies in Accounting and Business*, 5(1), 15-29.
- Saxena, A. (2019). The integral role of forensic accountants in fraud investigations. *International Journal of Forensic Accounting*.
- Singleton, T. & Flesher, D.L. (2003). A 25 years retrospective on the IIA's SAC project. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 18(1), 39-53.
- Smith, J., et al. (2022). Forensic accountants in the fight against fraud: Strategies and techniques. *Journal of Forensic Accounting Research*, 7(2), 101-120.
- Sullivan, J. (2021). Forensic accounting: A practical approach to financial investigation. *The Forensic Accountant Journal*.
- Sylvester, E.T. (2018). The relevance of forensic accounting; issues in accounting and auditing practice in Nigeria. *Journal of Humanities and social science*, 23(7), 17-24.
- Timbee, K. (2011). *Understanding financial crime and fraud: A comprehensive guide* (1st ed.). Cape Town, South Africa: Juta & Company.
- Umar, U.H., Haron, M.H., & Kurawa, J.M. (2021). Detection and prevention of fraud through Islamic inheritance: The case of Islamic inheritance in Nigeria. in Rafay, A. (ed.), *Handbook of Research on Theory and Practice of Financial Crimes*, IGI Global.

Wells, J. T. (2013). Financial crime: The role of forensic accounting in prevention and detection. *Journal of Economic Crime Management*, 10(1), 58-73.

Wells, J. T. (2014). Principles of fraud examination. *Fraud Magazine*.

Yakubu, B. Z. & Oyedokun, G.E. (2021). Enhancing Public Confidence in Audit Report of Listed Companies in Nigeria through Forensic Audit. *Journal of Forensic Accounting and Fraud Investigation*, 6(1), 83-103, a publication of Association of forensic Accounting Researchers, available at www.afarng.org

Zimbelman, M. F., & Smith, G. S. (2019). Forensic accounting: A guide to financial investigations. *Journal of Forensic Studies in Accounting and Business*.